

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AND FRACTURE BEHAVIORS OF ALUMINUM MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Al / SiC, Al / Al₂O₃, and Al / SiC / Al₂O₃ composites are fabricated by the direct squeeze infiltration method. Mechanical properties such as Young's modulus and tensile strength of MMCs are improved up to 70 % and 60 % respectively by the addition of reinforcements. Microstructure shows that the uniform distribution of reinforcements and good bonding between reinforcements and matrix alloy. Fracture surface represents a ductile failure mode on microstructural level. Failure mechanisms of discontinuous MMCs are suggested by In-situ SEM observation. Failure mechanism of fibrous MMCs can be summarized as follows; (i) the formation of microcracks at the fiber ends and in the matrix, (ii) the formation of major crack by multiplications and coalescences of microcracks, and (iii) the induction of major crack to fracture.

KEYWORDS : Metal Matrix Composite ; Squeeze Casting ; Hybrid ; Failure mechanism ; In-situ SEM.

1. INTRODUCTION

Discontinuously reinforced metal matrix composites are becoming important structural materials in aerospace, aircraft, and automobile industries due to their high specific mechanical properties at room and elevated temperatures, high wear resistance, and processability by standard metallurgical fabrication techniques [1-3]. Unfortunately, their low ductility and fracture toughness restricts their applications as structural components. Therefore, detailed failure mechanisms should be identified with the view of improving mechanical properties of discontinuous MMCs in order to widen their application areas.

Many reports on the characterization of mechanical properties of discontinuous MMCs have

been published [4,5]. According to them, mechanical properties, such as Young's modulus and strength, have been improved about 50 ~ 100 % by the incorporation of reinforcements. However, ductility has been deteriorated remarkably [1,4].

Metal matrix composites used to fail in different ways from polymer matrix composites because of the presence of intermetallic compounds in the matrix and at interfaces, and stress concentration originated from differences in thermal expansion coefficients and stiffnesses of the constituents.

Recently, much attention has been paid to the failure mechanism of MMCs with a view of improving their ductility and fracture toughness [6-14]. Attempts for the investigation of the detailed failure mechanisms have indicated that several factors, including the reinforcement - matrix interface, cracking of reinforcements and intermetallic compounds, microstructural inhomogeneities, play important roles in composite failures [6-10]. Localized plastic flow [10] and severe stress concentration at whisker ends [6,7,10] result in microstructural damage in the form of void initiation and growth, and this damage lead to premature failure and low ductility. According to [6], fibers are preventing crack propagation, therefore, additional damages occur by the formation of other matrix cracks rather than by the propagation of existing cracks. In general, final failure is due to the debonding.

The dominant failure mechanism in Al / SiC particulate composites is a failure in the matrix, i.e., failure as occurring through the matrix [13], and a mixed failure with crack propagation through particles, interfaces and the matrix [11]. In our lab [12], effects of interface conditions on crack nucleation and propagation were studied.

However it is difficult to identify the dominant mechanism because many mechanisms are involved in the failure behavior and the lack of In-situ observations during the deformation and fracture processes.

The objective of present study is to provide dynamic observations of the crack initiation and propagation mechanisms in Al / SiC whisker and Al / SiC / Al₂O₃ composites by the use of In-situ SEM techniques. In this study, composite materials are fabricated by the direct squeeze infiltration method. As fabricated and properly heat treated (T6) composites are investigated. The dominant failure mechanism are proposed and the effects of matrix properties on failure mechanism are also discussed.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Fabrication of Discontinuously Reinforced MMCs For the fabrication of Al / SiC, Al / Al₂O₃, and Al / SiC / Al₂O₃ composite materials, a 6061 aluminum alloy was used as a matrix. Specifications of SiC whiskers and alumina fibers are shown in Table 1 [18,19]. Composite materials were fabricated by the direct squeeze infiltration method. To make a preform, the paper making process was adapted and 5 - 10 wt % silica colloid was used as a binder. A preform was preheated to 700 °C. Molten Al alloy was overheated to 770 ± 10 °C and then infiltrated into the preform under the pressure of 25 MPa. Composite materials with various volume fractions were successfully fabricated. Typical microstructures of composites are represented in Figure 1. It is demonstrated that the reinforcements are distributed uniformly. Specimens were heat treated under T6 condition (540 °C for 4 hours, water quenching, 180 °C for 4 hours, and air cooling).

2.2 Mechanical test Tensile tests were performed with MTS 809 Axial Torsional Test System. Test were load controlled and the load rate was 30 N / sec. Strain gages were attached in the center of the gage length section. After tensile tests, fracture surfaces were examined by SEM.

2.3 In-situ wedge loading tests in SEM Direct observation during the deformation and fracture processes were performed in SEM, Cambridge Instrument Model Stereoscan 250 Mks, with the wedge loading stage. The wedge loading stage used for the In-situ SEM observation was inserted into the vacuum chamber of the SEM replacing the standard sample

stage as shown in Figure 2. Load is applied directly on the specimen using loading arm of the stage connected to outside of vacuum chamber. By gradual inserting of the wedge into the specimen, Mechanisms of crack nucleation and propagation on the surface of specimen can be observed directly through SEM with the wedge loading stage.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Mechanical Properties The effective stiffness and tensile strength of random short fiber composites is strongly dependent upon many variables such as the fiber orientation, the aspect ratio of fibers, mechanical properties of fibers and matrix, the crack sensitivity of matrix, and bonding conditions between fibers and matrix. Mechanical properties are shown in Figure 3. By additions of SiC whiskers, Al_2O_3 fibers, and SiC- Al_2O_3 systems, elastic moduli were improved up to 70 %, 40 %, and 30%, respectively.

Tensile strength was improved linearly up to 60 % in Al/SiC, 25 % in Al/ Al_2O_3 , and 40 % in Al/SiC/ Al_2O_3 . In Al/SiC, UTS starts to decrease when volume fraction is over 0.23. The decreases of UTS are mainly due to the imperfect infiltration caused by a low applied pressure (25 MPa). The imperfect infiltration was found by the examination of fracture surfaces through SEM. But in Al/ Al_2O_3 composites, no remarkable decreases are observed at high volume fractions. A low applied pressure, 25 MPa, is good enough for the fabrication of Al/SiC and Al/ Al_2O_3 composites, also, for Al/SiC/ Al_2O_3 composites up to 0.2 and 0.25 or more volume fraction, respectively.

3.2 Fractographic study Fracture surfaces of Al/SiC composites are shown in Figure 4. Figure 4 (a) illustrates typical fracture surfaces with 15 vol. % of reinforcements. Al/SiC composite is well bonded because of few fiber pull-outs, see (1), and less fibers in the quantities corresponding to their volume fraction [15,16]. Few cleavage facets, see (2), and many dimples, see (3), which are associated with the ductile fracture of the matrix are found from fracture surfaces, consequently, the failure mode is brittle macroscopically, but is ductile on microstructural level.

The extent of void growth determines the ductility of material. If this growth is very limited, dimples are very small and the material behaves in a brittle manner. Fracture surface of Al/20 vol.% SiC composite is shown in Figure 4 (b). Reduced amounts of dimples and more cleavage facets imply that the failure mode is getting brittle as the fiber volume fraction increases.

Typical fracture surfaces of Al/ Al_2O_3 composites are illustrated in Figure 5. Many dimples and fibers in the middle of the dimples are frequently observed in Figure 5 (a) and (b). Also, fiber breakages, see (1), and debondings, see (2), are shown in Figure 5 (b). Although few debondings are found, the overall bonding condition is good. A fiber pull-out in the center of the dimple are rarely observed, see (3). According to reference [17], the dimple formation at fiber ends is affected by the bonding condition, i.e., a fiber pull-out are found in the middle of the dimple when bonding is poor. A schematic interpretation of the difference in the dimple formation is given in Figure 6. From dimples around axial fibers, most voids are nucleated at fiber ends and propagate toward the matrix.

3.3 In-situ SEM analysis Various factors, including the interface between reinforcements and the matrix, reinforcement cracking, brittle cracking of precipitates, and microstructural inhomogeneities, are closely associated with the composite failure. Although it is difficult to identify clearly the dominant mechanism and contributions of each mechanism, dynamic observation by the use of In-situ SEM make it possible to suggest the dominant mechanism and its contributions.

3.3.1 Failure mechanisms of the as-fabricated Al/SiC composite In the as-fabricated Al/SiC composite, failure is processed by the formation and propagations of major crack. As

the applied load increases, lots of microcracks start to be initiated near the precrack tip. Figure 7 (a) and (b) show the surfaces of specimen before and after loading. A clean surface without any damages is observed before loading in Figure 7 (a). As shown in Figure 7(b), microcracks are formed near fibers, see (1), at fiber ends, see (2), and in the matrix, see (3). Microcracks are apt to be initiated perpendicular to the applied stress axis and at high stress concentration regions, such as at or near fiber ends. Owing to low yield strength of the unaged matrix, microcracks can be formed in the matrix. From the morphology of microcracks, i.e., the size and extent of elongation, it can be regarded that the microcracks at and near fiber ends are initiated earlier than those in the matrix. The breakage of the transverse fiber is also observed, see (4). Lots of microcracks are found specially in fiber clustering regions and these microcracks seem to play important roles in the premature failure of Al / SiC composites.

As the applied stress increases, the major crack begins to be initiated by the multiplication and coalescence of microcracks. The initiation process of major crack is illustrated in Figure 8. Microcracks are formed in fiber clustering regions (Figure 8 (a)). They propagate into the matrix and other microcracks are formed at the matrix as the loading continues (Figure 8 (b)). Finally, the initiation of major crack occurs as linking microcracks in the matrix and fiber clustering regions (Figure 8 (c)). The propagation of major crack is shown in Figure 9. At high applied load, more microcracks are initiated at high stress concentration sites in front of the major crack tip (Figure 9 (a)). As load increases, a submajor crack is formed by linkages of microcracks ahead of crack tip (Figure 9 (b)). Finally, the major crack propagates as linking a submajor crack to the major crack as shown in Figure 9 (c).

Failure mechanisms of the as-fabricated Al / SiC composite are summarized as followings: (i) As the loading increases, microcracks start to be initiated at fiber ends and near fibers. And some of those propagate into the matrix. (ii) And then, microcracks are also formed in the matrix. Microcracks at the fiber ends and near fibers start to be linked to matrix cracks. (iii) As loading continues, the major crack is initiated by the multiplication and coalescence of microcracks. (iv) The major crack propagates as linking microcracks which are initiated and coalesced in front of the crack tip. (v) This major crack induces Al/SiC composite material to the final fracture.

3.3.2 Failure mechanisms of the heat treated Al / SiC composite A 6061 aluminum alloy which is used as the matrix material in this study is an age hardenable material. For the maximum mechanical properties, Al / SiC composites were solution treated and aged. Due to the changes in mechanical properties of matrix alloy, failure mechanisms of the heat treated composite are different from those of the as-fabricated. Detailed failure processes of the heat treated Al / SiC composite are illustrated in Figure 10.

Failure process in the heat treated Al / SiC composite is summarized as followings: (i) First, in front of the precrack tip, microcracks are initiated at fiber ends and grow to form the major crack. (ii) Due to the stress concentration near the crack tip, more microcracks are formed and advanced to some extent into the matrix. (iii) The major crack propagates abruptly by the weakest linkage of microcracks and this crack propagation leads to the catastrophic failure of the heat treated composite.

3.3.3 Failure mechanisms of the as-fabricated Al / SiC / Al₂O₃ composite Failure processes of hybrid composite are illustrated in Figure 11. The major crack is formed at the center of the precrack. The surface of specimen before loading is represented in Figure 11 (a). As shown in Figure 11 (b), microcracks start to be initiated at fiber ends and linked each other because of high stress concentration. Highly magnified Figure 12 (a) shows that the crack forms in the brittle part due to aggregation of reinforcements before the creation of crack at the crack tip. And then, as shown in Figure 12 (b), with linkage of major crack, final fracture occurs along precracked Al₂O₃ fiber region. Also, a long transverse Al₂O₃ fiber in front of the crack tip acts as a barrier from crack propagation. In consequence, the major crack changes the propagation path due to load transfer of transverse fibers (Figure 11 (c)).

3.3.4 Comparison of mechanism General crack initiation process in the heat treated composite is similar to the as-fabricated. However, there are two differences in failure mechanisms. One is the amount of microcrack which are formed during failure. A great deal of microcracks are initiated in the matrix during the failure process in the as-fabricated composite, less microcracks in the matrix are observed in the heat treated composite (see Figure 7 and 10). It seems to be strongly related to mechanical properties of the matrix alloy. Due to lower yield strength of the as-fabricated matrix alloy, more microcracks can be initiated in the matrix. Initiation of matrix cracks is often restricted in the heat treated composite because of increased yield strength by precipitation hardening. Another difference is the type of crack propagation. The major crack propagates gradually as linking to the submajor crack in as-fabricated. In the heat treated composite, smaller plastic zone resulted from higher yield strength limits crack propagation. Therefore, the major crack is advanced catastrophically by the sudden crack nucleation and propagation as the applied stress approaches composite strength. Comparisons between failure processes of both composites represent that mechanical properties of matrix alloy affect failure mechanisms of composite. In Al matrix composites, proper heat treatment should be necessary for the best quality of composites.

From dynamic observation of failure process in both Al / SiC composites, it is found that failure is started by formation of microcracks, and the fiber clustering region and irregular morphology of reinforcements, for example, large particle in whiskers, can be preferred crack initiation sites. Premature failure which deteriorates the ductility and fracture toughness of discontinuous MMCs is likely to take place in these areas. Consequently, the ductility of discontinuous MMCs can be improved by even distribution of reinforcements, minimized fiber damages during the fabrication, and the uniform morphology of reinforcements, i.e., all whisker shaped reinforcements.

4. CONCLUSIONS

1. Al / SiC, Al / Al₂O₃, and Al / SiC / Al₂O₃ composites with various volume fractions were successfully fabricated by squeeze infiltration method. Microstructure shows the uniform distribution of reinforcements and good bonding .
2. Mechanical properties, such as Young's modulus and tensile strength, are improved up to 70 % by the addition of reinforcement.
3. Failure mechanisms of the as-fabricated Al / SiC and Al / SiC / Al₂O₃ composites are summarized that i) the initiation of major crack by the multiplication and coalescence of microcracks, ii) the propagation of major crack as linking microcracks in front of the major crack tip, and iii) the induction of major crack to the final fracture.
4. Possible failure mechanisms of the heat treated Al / SiC composite include i) the formation of major crack at the precrack tip by the coalescence of microcracks, ii) initiations of microcracks ahead of the major crack tip, and iii) the catastrophic failure due to the abrupt propagation of the major crack by the weakest linkage of microcracks.
5. Differences in failure mechanisms of both the as fabricated and the heat treated composites are amounts of microcracks and the type of crack propagation. And they are closely related to mechanical properties of the matrix alloy
6. Optimized heat treatment of matrix alloy and uniform distribution and morphology of reinforcements play very important roles in improving mechanical properties of Al matrix composites.

5. REFERENCES

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TABLE 1 Specifications of SiC whisker and Al₂O₃ fiber [18,19]

Material	Composition (wt%)	Density (g/cm ³)	Diameter (μm)	Length (μm)	Aspect ratio (l/d)	Tensile strength (GPa)	Young's modulus (GPa)	Use temp. stability to ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
Al ₂ O ₃ (Saffil RFGGrade)	Al ₂ O ₃ : 96 SiO ₂ : 4	3.3	1.5 - 6.6*	3 - 110*	4 - 38*	2.0	310	1600
			Av. 3.5	70	20			
SiC (Toka- whisker)	SiC : 100	3.2	0.3 - 0.6*	5 - 15*	10 - 25*	3 - 14	400 - 700 (in air)	1600
			Av. 0.45	8.4	13.5			

* ; Measured values from microstructures.

FIGURE 1. Microstructure of
 (a) Al / 15 vol.% SiC,
 (b) Al / 15 vol.% Al₂O₃ , and
 (c) Al / 5 vol.% SiC / 10 vol.% Al₂O₃
 composites fabricated by
 the squeeze infiltration method

FIGURE 2. (a) The wedge loading stage (b) DCB specimen used for In - situ SEM observation

FIGURE 3. Effect of the volume fraction of reinforcement on mechanical properties of of MMCs

FIGURE 4. Fracture surface of (a) Al / 15 vol.% SiC and (b) Al / 20 vol.% SiC composite

FIGURE 5. Fracture surface of Al / 25 vol.% Al₂O₃ composite (a) overall view and (b) high magnification

FIGURE 6. Schematic illustration of dimple formation in (a) well bonded and (b) poor bonded composite [17]

FIGURE 7. Initiation of microcracks (a) before loading and (b) after loading

FIGURE 8. Initiation process of the major crack in the as fabricated Al / SiC composite

- Formation of microcracks at fiber clustering regions
- Formation of microcracks in the matrix
- Initiation of the major crack by the linkage of microcracks

FIGURE 9. Propagation process of the major crack in the as fabricated Al / SiC composite

- Initiation of more microcracks ahead of the crack tip
- Formation of the submajor crack
- Propagation of the major crack

FIGURE 10. Failure process in the heat treated Al / SiC composite
 (a) Before loading
 (b) Initiation of microcracks in front of the crack tip
 (c) Formation of the major crack
 (d) Initiation of more microcracks and their propagation
 (e) Catastrophc failure by fast nucleation and propagation of microcracks

FIGURE 11. Failure process in the heat treated Al / SiC composite
(a) Before loading
(b) Initiation of microcracks
(c) propagation of the major crack and failure

FIGURE 12. High magnification of initiation of microcracks